

Cu (II) and Ni (II) Chelates of some Orthohydroxy Diketones as Ligands

D. Chakravarti, Minati Saha and Apurba Krishna Baral

Copper (II) and Ni(II) chelates of some new ortho-hydroxy-(1 : 7, 1 : 8, 1 : 9, 1 : 10)-diketones have been described.

The hydroxy diketones of the type (I) have been synthesised by Chakravarti *et al.*¹

where $\text{R} = \text{R}_1 = \text{OH}$ and OCH_3 ; $\text{R}_2 = \text{H, Cl, Br}$; $n = 5, 6, 7, 8$.

Among the various diketones described some 2-hydroxy compounds are interesting as they contain suitable donor atoms favourably placed so as to co-ordinate with bivalent metal ions (preferably transitional) and this property of the 2-hydroxy diketones may be utilised for the gravimetric determination of metal ions. Chelate complexes are formed in which the metal is bound to the organic ligand through two oxygen atoms; to one by an ionic bond and to the other by a coordinate bond. Six membered ring structure (II) may thus result with structural unit very similar to that present in complexes formed by salicylaldehyde and orthohydroxy aromatic ketones^{2,3}.

1. *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **42**, 607; 1966, **43**, 33; 1969, **46**, 351, 743.
2. M. F. Barker, *Chem. News*, 1925, **130**, 99.
3. Pfeiffer, Golther and Angern, *Ber.*, 1927, **60**, 305.

It has been observed experimentally that these newly synthesised organic compounds form complexes with Cu^{++} , Ni^{++} , Co^{++} , UO_2^{++} , Cr^{+++} , Al^{+++} ions. In the present communication have been described the preparation and properties of the chelates with Cu^{++} and Ni^{++} ions.

EXPERIMENTAL

All reagents used were of A.R. grade.

Methods of estimation : Copper was estimated gravimetrically as cupric oxide after decomposing the chelate with conc. HNO_3 . Nickel was estimated as nickel dimethyl glyoxime.

Methods of preparation of Cu—chelates : The solution of the diketone in alcohol was mixed with the solution of copper acetate in alcohol in the mole ratio of 1 : 1. The pH of the solution was maintained in between 5.6 to 6 using sodium acetate buffer. The solution was refluxed for two and a half hours. It was then cooled, filtered, washed with distilled water and then with warm rectified spirit, and dried in vacuo.

Method of preparation of Ni—chelates : The solution of the diketones in alcohol was mixed with the solution of nickel acetate in alcohol in the mole ratio 1 : 1. The pH of the solution was maintained in between 7 to 7.5 using sodium acetate buffer and then with the addition of a very dilute ($N/100$) solution of sodium hydroxide slowly drop by drop. The solution was refluxed for two and a half hours. It was then cooled, filtered, washed with distilled water and then with warm rectified spirit and dried in vacuo.

TABLE I
Copper Chelates

Name of the Legend	Compound	Color	Required %	Analytical results	Found %
1. 1,7 Bis[2,4 dihydroxy phenyl]-heptane 1,7 dione	$C_{19}H_{18}O_6Cu$	green	C, 56.22; H, 4.44; Cu, 15.66	C, 56.43; H, 4.28; Cu, 15.60	
	$R = R_1 = OH$ $R_2 = H, n = 5$				
2. 1,7 Bis[2-hydroxy-4-methoxy-phenyl]-heptane 1,7 dione	$C_{21}H_{22}O_8Cu$	green	C, 58.13; H, 5.08; Cu, 14.65	C, 58.30; H, 5.20; Cu, 14.77	
	$R = OH, R_1 = OCH_3$ $R_2 = H, n = 5$				
3. 1,7 Bis[2,4 dihydroxy-5-chlorophenyl]-heptane 1,7 dione	$C_{19}H_{16}O_6Cl_2Cu$	pale green	C, 48.04; H, 3.37; Cu, 13.39	C, 47.70; H, 3.22; Cu, 13.62	
	$R = R_1 = OH$ $R_2 = Cl, n = 5$				
4. 1,8 Bis[2,4 dihydroxy phenyl]-octane 1,8 dione	$C_{20}H_{20}O_6Cu$	pale green	C, 57.22; H, 4.77; Cu, 15.14	C, 56.92; H, 4.81; Cu, 15.09	
	$R = R_1 = OH$ $R_2 = H, n = 6$				
5. 1,8 Bis[2-hydroxy-4-methoxy-phenyl]-octane 1,8 dione	$C_{22}H_{24}O_8Cu$	green	C, 58.99; H, 5.36; Cu, 14.19	C, 58.68; H, 5.22; Cu, 14.28	
	$R = OH, R_1 = OCH_3$ $R_2 = H, n = 6$				
6. 1,8 Bis[2,4 dihydroxy-5-chlorophenyl]-octane 1,8 dione	$C_{20}H_{18}O_6Cl_2Cu$	yellowish green	C, 49.14; H, 3.69; Cu, 13.00	C, 49.34; H, 3.82; Cu, 13.22	
	$R = R_1 = OH$ $R_2 = Cl, n = 6$				
7. 1,9 Bis[2,4-dihydroxy phenyl]-nonane 1,9 dione	$C_{21}H_{22}O_6Cu$	pale green	C, 58.13; H, 5.08; Cu, 14.65	C, 57.98; H, 4.88; Cu, 14.48	
	$R = R_1 = OH$ $R_2 = H, n = 7$				
8. 1,9 Bis[2-hydroxy-4-methoxy-phenyl]-nonane 1,9 dione	$C_{23}H_{26}O_8Cu$	green	C, 59.80; H, 5.63; Cu, 13.76	C, 59.61; H, 5.82; Cu, 13.69	
	$R = OH, R_1 = OCH_3$ $R_2 = H, n = 7$				
9. 1,9 Bis[2,4-dihydroxy-5-chlorophenyl]-nonane 1,9 dione	$C_{21}H_{20}O_6Cl_2Cu$	green	C, 50.16; H, 3.98; Cu, 12.64	C, 49.95; H, 3.81; Cu, 12.94	
	$R = R_1 = OH$ $R_2 = Cl, n = 7$				
10. 1,10 Bis[2,4-dihydroxy phenyl]-decane 1,10 dione	$C_{22}H_{24}O_6Cu$	muddy green	C, 58.99; H, 5.36; Cu, 14.19	C, 58.72; H, 5.65; Cu, 14.11	
	$R = R_1 = OH$ $R_2 = H, n = 8$				
11. 1,10 Bis[2-hydroxy-4-methoxy-phenyl]-decane 1,10 dione	$C_{24}H_{28}O_8Cu$	green	C, 60.58; H, 5.89; Cu, 13.36	C, 60.18; H, 5.96; Cu, 13.57	
	$R = OH, R_1 = OCH_3$ $R_2 = H, n = 8$				
12. 1,10 Bis[2,4-dihydroxy-5-chlorophenyl]-decane 1,10 dione	$C_{22}H_{22}O_6Cl_2Cu$	moss green	C, 51.11; H, 4.26; Cu, 12.29	C, 50.96; H, 4.12; Cu, 12.18	
	$R = R_1 = OH$ $R_2 = Cl, n = 8$				

TABLE II
Nickel Chelates

Name of the Ligand	Compound	Color	Required %	Analytical results	Found %
1. 1,7 Bis[2,4 dihydroxy phenyl]-heptane 1,7 dione	$C_{19}H_{18}O_6Ni$	dark green	C, 56.89; H, 4.49; Ni, 14.65	C, 56.68; H, 5.05; Ni, 14.61	
2. 1,7 Bis[2-hydroxy-4-methoxy-phenyl]-heptane 1,7 dione	$C_{21}H_{22}O_6Ni$	bright green	C, 58.78; H, 5.13; Ni, 13.70	C, 58.51; H, 4.92; Ni, 13.62	
3. 1,7 Bis[2,4 dihydroxy-5-chlorophenyl]-heptane 1,7 dione	$C_{19}H_{16}O_6Cl_2Ni$	green	C, 48.53; H, 3.41; Ni, 12.49	C, 48.71; H, 3.25; Ni, 12.76	
4. 1,8 Bis[2,4 dihydroxy phenyl]-octane 1,8 dione	$C_{20}H_{20}O_6Ni$	pale green	C, 57.88; H, 4.82; Ni, 14.16	C, 57.65; H, 4.60; Ni, 14.41	
5. 1,8 Bis[2, hydroxy-4-methoxy phenyl]-octane 1,8 dione	$C_{22}H_{24}O_6Ni$	dark green	C, 59.64; H, 5.42; Ni, 13.26	C, 59.45; H, 5.29; Ni, 13.19	
6. 1,8 Bis[2,4 dihydroxy-5-chlorophenyl]-octane 1,8 dione	$C_{20}H_{18}O_6Cl_2Ni$	pale green	C, 49.63; H, 3.72; Ni, 12.13	C, 49.44; H, 3.50; Ni, 12.45	
7. 1,9 Bis[2,4 dihydroxy phenyl]-nonane 1,9 dione	$C_{21}H_{24}O_6Ni$	pale green	C, 58.79; H, 5.13; Ni, 13.70	C, 58.95; H, 4.98; Ni, 13.49	
8. 1,9 Bis[2-hydroxy-4-methoxy-phenyl]-nonane 1,9 dione	$C_{23}H_{26}O_6Ni$	pale green	C, 60.42; H, 5.69; Ni, 12.85	C, 60.21; H, 5.49; Ni, 12.79	
9. 1,9 Bis[2,4 dihydroxy-5-chlorophenyl]-nonane 1,9 dione	$C_{21}H_{20}O_6Cl_2Ni$	green	C, 50.63; H, 4.02; Ni, 11.80	C, 50.15; H, 3.98; Ni, 12.01	
10. 1,10 Bis[2,4 dihydroxy-phenyl]-decane 1,10 dione	$C_{22}H_{24}O_6Ni$	pale green	C, 59.50; H, 5.41; Ni, 13.23	C, 59.28; H, 5.30; Ni, 12.95	
11. 1,10 Bis[2-hydroxy-4-methoxy phenyl]-decane 1,10 dione	$C_{24}H_{28}O_6Ni$	pale green	C, 61.19; H, 5.95; Ni, 12.48	C, 60.94; H, 5.81; Ni, 12.47	
12. 1, 10 Bis[2,4 dihydroxy-5-chlorophenyl]-decane 1,10 dione	$C_{22}H_{22}O_6Cl_2Ni$	pale green	C, 51.59; H, 4.30; Ni, 11.48	C, 51.81; H, 4.45; Ni, 11.41	

Chemical Laboratory,
University College of Science,
Calcutta-9.

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